

IRENA MAJSTORVIĆ, PHD*

FAMILY LAW AND THE EU - AT THE CROSSROADS? **

Abstract:

Family law is a particular branch of law, under considerable influence of tradition, culture, customs and religion. As a consequence, it has long been excluded from the processes of European integration. However, during the last decades the shift in legal paradigm occurred - from complete neglect to the mainstreaming the issues of family law and human rights into the European Union policies. The Union clearly shows great interest in the family law and the expectation that it shall continue to do so even more vigorously leads us to the doubts, as considered in this paper.

The three main issues include: the significance and the value of the Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union from the family law aspect; the relationship between multilevel protection systems and finally, the direction and scope of future development. Namely, it seems at this point that the development of EU interest in the issues of family law has reached a turning point. The most realistic scenarios for the future in the view of the author are refocusing on economic issues; further and concrete committing to human rights issues and finally, maintaining the status quo, which is found to be the most likely scenario.

Keywords: *Family law, human rights, European Union, Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union, Council of Europe, harmonisation and unification, multilevel protection systems*

* Associate Professor, Chair of Family Law, Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, E-mail: irena.majstorovic@pravo.hr

** This article has been written within the scope of the research project "New Croatian Legal System" of the Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb.

I. INTRODUCTORY NOTES

Family law is a very particular branch of law, considerably influenced by tradition, culture, customs and religion. As such, it has long been excluded from the processes of European integration. However, it is now time to confirm that such „isolation“ is neither possible, nor meaningful. Moreover, as Perišin correctly states, an activity within the EU which would be completely outside the scope of the European law is almost incomprehensible.¹ It is also beyond any doubt that the subject matter of regulation of the European law today includes the issues which were long considered to be the „centre of national sovereignty“, such as the national and international human rights guarantees.²

This trend has been evident in the development of the EU interest in the family law issues. Namely, during the last decades the shift in legal paradigm occurred - from complete neglect to the mainstreaming the issues of family law and human rights into the EU policies. The fact that the EU clearly shows great interest in the family law and the expectation that it shall continue to do so even more vigorously, leads us to the main doubts, as considered in this paper.

Firstly, which is the significance and the value of the Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union; is it just the first step to a much more elaborated system of protection of human rights? Secondly, which is the relationship between multilevel protection systems; and could it be envisaged that the EU shall take over the precedence of the Council of Europe being the most important organisation in Europe for the protection of human rights? And thirdly, which could be the direction and scope of future development? The aim of the paper is to present some views on the mentioned relevant issues of the protection of human rights from the family law perspective, and hopefully to serve as incentive for future considerations.

II. DEVELOPMENT OF EU INTEREST IN THE ISSUES OF FAMILY LAW

The rise of interest of the European Union (earlier the European (Economic) Community) in the family law, and particularly as regards substantive family law, could be divided into three phases.³ The first, from the establishment of the Communities and the Treaty of

¹ T. Perišin, 'Ima li Europska unija ovlast regulirati privatno (posebice ugovorno) pravo? (Does the European Union have the competence to regulate private (especially contract) Law?)', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu*, 62, 5-6, 2012, p. 1799.

² Perišin, pp. 1799-1800.

³ On the development from the standpoint of international private law, see: M. Župan and V. Puljko, 'Shaping European international family law', *Slovenian law review*, 23, 7, 2010, pp. 30-39.

Rome⁴ in 1957 until the entry into force of the Treaty of Amsterdam⁵ in 1999. The second, from 1999 until the last revision of the founding treaties, that is the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon⁶ in 2009. And the third phase is the present time, marked by lots of initiatives of the European institutions.

From the establishment, the European community was dedicated to the economic issues and as Defeis puts it “little attention was paid to the protection of human rights ... (which) were being addressed in other forums”⁷, such as the United Nations. To be more precise, the Treaty establishing the European Economic Community did not even mention fundamental rights at all.⁸ Some commentators find it to be a “stunning omission”, but even they consider that it can be explained by the “drafter’s vision of the nature of the institution being created; that is, one of limited competence, primarily concerned with economic matters, that would not unduly encroach on the rights of the Member States”⁹.

However, the Court of Justice of the European Communities (as it then was, further: ECJ) took another path, passing numerous judgements in which it established the principle of supremacy of Community law over the domestic law of the Member states. Hence, it established “a new legal order for member states”. For example, in the case *Van Gend en Loos v Netherlands* in 1963¹⁰ the ECJ draw a conclusion that “the Community constitutes a new legal order of international law for the benefit of which the states have limited their sovereign rights, *albeit within limited fields* (emphasis I.M.)¹¹, and the subjects of which comprise not only Member States but also their nationals. Independently of the legisla-

⁴ Treaty establishing the European Economic Community (1957), not published in the Official Journal. It is available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=URISERV:xy0023>, (accessed 1st September 2015).

⁵ Treaty of Amsterdam amending the Treaty on European Union, the Treaties establishing the European Communities and related acts, Official Journal C 340, 10.11.1997, pp. 1-144.

⁶ Treaty of Lisbon amending the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community, signed at Lisbon, 13 December 2007, Official Journal C 306, 17.12.2007, p. 1–271. See also: Consolidated version of the Treaty on European Union, Official Journal C 326, 26.10.2012, p. 13–390 and Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Official Journal C 326, 26.10.2012, pp. 47–390.

⁷ E. F. Defeis, ‘Human Rights and the European Court of Justice: An Appraisal’, *Fordham International Law Journal*, 31, 5, 2007, p. 1105.

⁸ It should be said that the phrase fundamental rights is not synonymous to human rights, since e.g. the companies may claim them too. Cf. Douglas-Scott, S.: The European Union and human rights after the Treaty of Lisbon, *Human rights law review*, 11, 4, 2011, p. 651., note 26. In this text the phrases are used interchangeably.

⁹ Defeis, *Fordham International Law Journal*, p. 1106.

¹⁰ *Case C-26/62, Van Gend and Loos* [1963] ECR English special edition p. 12.

¹¹ It should be noticed that even now, half a century later, it still remains an open questions which are those limited fields. The same: Perišin, p. 1806.

tion of Member States, Community law therefore not only imposes obligations on individuals but is also intended to confer upon them rights which become part of their legal heritage. These rights arise not only where they are expressly granted by the Treaty, but also by reason of obligations which the Treaty imposes in a clearly defined way upon individuals as well as upon the Member States and upon the institutions of the Community.”¹²

A year later, in case *Costa v. ENEL*¹³ it stated that “... the EEC Treaty has created its own legal system which ... became an integral part of the legal systems of the Member States and which their courts are bound to apply.”¹⁴ It continued that “[t]he executive force of Community law cannot vary from one State to another in deference to subsequent domestic laws, without jeopardising the attainment of the objectives of the Treaty.”¹⁵

In 1969, in case *Stauder v. Ulm*,¹⁶ the ECJ found that fundamental rights form part of the Community law, in that way “reaffirmed its role as a guardian of human rights within the framework of Community law.”¹⁷ This idea was further elaborated in *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft* case, when the Court stated that the Community law is “inspired by the constitutional tradition of member states.”¹⁸ As Defeis correctly notices, “the substance of these decisions had now been incorporated into the subsequent treaties of the EU.”¹⁹

However, as regards the family law in particular, the first real milestone was the Treaty of Amsterdam, which entered into force in 1999. It brought significant changes in the Union’s structure, and what is of interest for the topic of this paper, the judicial co-operation was for the first time to be regulated by secondary legislation, instead of inter-country conventions, as was the case in the past. In that very year, the ECJ confirmed that the family law issues fall exclusively within the competence of the member states. In the case *Johannes v. Johannes*, it elaborated: “... Those rights are governed by the rules of private law and family law applying in the Member states, which fall within the competence of those Member states.”²⁰

¹² *Case C-26/62, Van Gend and Loos* [1963] ECR English special edition p. 12.

¹³ *Case C-6/64 Costa v ENEL* [1964] ECR English special edition p.585.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 593.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 594.

¹⁶ *Case C-29/69 Stauder* [1969] ECR 419

¹⁷ H. Stalford, ‘Concepts of family under EU law – lessons from the ECHR’, *International law of law, policy and the family*, vol. 16, 2002, p. 425.

¹⁸ *Case C-11/70 Internationale Handelsgesellschaft mbH* [1970] ECR 1134

¹⁹ Defeis, *Fordham International Law Journal*, p. 1110. Article 6 Para 3 of the Consolidated Treaty on European Union defines as follows: Fundamental rights, as guaranteed by the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and as they result from the constitutional traditions common to the Member States, shall constitute general principles of the Union’s law.

²⁰ *Case C-430/97 Jutta Johannes v. Harmut Johannes*, [1999] ECR I-3475, para. 18.

Slowly and still gradually, the issues of family law were being tackled more and more, at first in the “marginal areas”, particularly by linkage to the questions of free movement of family members and family reunification, but still without any concrete developments. Furthermore, the only explicit mention of family law in the founding treaties was until the Lisbon Treaty an excluding formulation. Namely, in accordance with Article 67 Para 5 Subpara 2 of the Treaty on the European Union, “the Council shall adopt ... measures provided for in Article 65 (that is measures in the field of judicial cooperation in civil matters having cross-border implications) with the exception of aspects relating to family law” (insertion and emphasis I.M.).²¹ Nevertheless, it was the time of EU’s “adopting a much more proactive role in the development and application of European family law and policy”.²²

The second milestone in the development of the EU interest in the family law was the Treaty of Lisbon which entered into force in 2009 and allowed for a political and legal paradigm shift. Two articles of the Treaty on the functioning of the European Union are to be particularly emphasised. First is Article 67 which confirms that Union shall constitute an Area of freedom, security and justice with respect for fundamental rights and the different legal systems and traditions of the Member States. The establishment of the Area had significant implications on family law and it has proven that „the EU has gone beyond being a Common Market, encompassing a much greater range of activities“.²³ It is in particular the issues of family law that deserve much attention in regards to the Area of freedom, security and justice, which is often overshadowed by more pressing problems, like the ones of the asylum procedures.

Second and by far the most important provision for the topic of this paper is Article 81, which defines that the Union shall develop judicial cooperation in civil matters having cross-border implications, based on the principle of mutual recognition of judgments and of decisions in extrajudicial cases and that such cooperation may include the adoption of measures for the approximation of the laws and regulations of the Member States.

Unlike other areas of law, upon which it is decided in ordinary procedure, it is defined in Paragraph 3 of the same article that „... *measures concerning family law with cross-border implications shall be established by the Council, acting in accordance with a special legislative procedure. The Council shall act unanimously after consulting the European Parliament.*“ Furthermore: „*The Council, on a proposal from the Commission, may adopt a decision determining those aspects of family law with cross-border implications which may be the subject of acts adopted by the ordinary legislative procedure. The Council shall act unanimously after consulting the European Parliament.*“

²¹ Consolidated versions of the Treaty on European Union and of the Treaty establishing the European Community, Official Journal C 321, 29.12.2006.

²² Stalford, *International law of law, policy and the family*, p. 410.

²³ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 648.

The proposal referred to in the second subparagraph shall be notified to the national Parliaments. If a national Parliament makes known its opposition within six months of the date of such notification, the decision shall not be adopted. In the absence of opposition, the Council may adopt the decision.“

It is yet to be seen whether national parliaments shall be able and willing, in cases of need, to protect national interests. Such a commitment requires knowledge and diplomatic and political skills. It is therefore very important that the significance of family law issues is always acknowledged and respected.

With the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon, another change happened. Namely, the change in the legal importance of the Charter of fundamental rights - it finally became of binding nature.²⁴ The impact of this document on the family law is further elaborated in the next chapter.

III. CHARTER OF FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS

The Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union²⁵ is a catalogue of rights, very similar to the European convention for the protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms and/or other international documents, the impact of which on family law has undoubtedly been significant.²⁶ The wording is not identical nor the rights are identical, but similarity is comprehensible and also expected.

There are two main issues I shall address in this part. Firstly, what was the reasoning behind adopting such a document and secondly, how important is it for the family law? It should be emphasised that even before the Charter became legally binding, the ECJ defined that the “principal aim of the Charter, as is apparent from its preamble, is to reaffirm ‘rights as they result, in particular, from the constitutional traditions and international obligations common to the Member States, the Treaty on European Union, the Community Treaties, the [ECHR], the Social Charters adopted by the Community and by the Council of Europe and the case-law of the Court ... and of the European Court of Human

²⁴ Article 6 Para 1 of the Treaty on European Union: The Union recognises the rights, freedoms and principles set out in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union of 7 December 2000, as adapted at Strasbourg, on 12 December 2007, which shall have the same legal value as the Treaties.

²⁵ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, Official Journal C 326, 26.10.2012, p. 391–407.

²⁶ S. Choudry and J. Herring, *‘European human rights and family law’*, Oregon, Hart publishing, Oxford and Portland, 2010, p. 1.

Rights.²⁷ As Stalford puts it, even the adoption of the Charter „further endorses the status of human rights at EU level“.²⁸

3.1 Family law provisions in the Charter

As regards the family law, there are several provisions worth mentioning.²⁹ First is Article 33 Para 1 which stipulates that the family shall enjoy legal, economic and social protection. This is a very important provision, which McGlynn finds to be recognition of the fact that Union law does impact on families and expresses an aim to seek to “protect” them.³⁰

It is also a reflection of several constitutional provisions of the member states which guarantee in their highest legal sources the protection of the state to marriage and the family.³¹ It should be accentuated that constitutional protection of family is a common notion in Europe, since 1919 when the German Weimar Constitution in its Article 119 emphasised it.³² As Jakovac-Lozić states, even in European constitutions which do not mention family explicitly, it is beyond any doubt protected by their civil and family-law codes as an institution upon which the real social values rest.³³

²⁷ Case C-540/03 *European Parliament v Council of the European Union* [2006] ECR I-05769, para. 38. Arguments to the contrary, that is the concept that „the Charter expands the interpretative scope of Union and law and policy and perhaps even its competence“ is offered by C. McGlynn, ‘Families and the European Union Charter of Fundamental Rights: progressive change or entrenching the status quo?’, *European Law Review*, vol. 26, no. 6, 2001, p. 586, 587.

²⁸ Stalford, *International law of law, policy and the family*, p. 412.

²⁹ For thorough analysis, see: A. Korać Graovac, ‘Povelja o temeljnim pravima Europske unije i obiteljsko pravo (Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union and family law)’, in: A. Korać Graovac and I. Majstorović (eds.), ‘*Europsko obiteljsko pravo (European family law)*’, Narodne novine, Zagreb, 2013, pp. 25-51.

³⁰ McGlynn, *European Law Review*, p. 587.

³¹ Examples could be found for instance in German and in Croatian Constitution. Reference is to be made also to the so-called Solange Saga, namely, Germany accepts the supremacy of EU law only „as long as“ (German: solange) the EU law guarantees the fundamental rights as defined in German Basic Law (Grundgesetz), cf. Re Wuensche Handelsgesellschaft, BVerfG decision of 22 October 1986 [1987] 3 CMLR 225,265). More on the position of family in constitutions, D. Jakovac-Lozić, ‘Obitelj - mjesto i zaštita u europskim ustavima (Family - Its Position and Protection in European Constitutions)’, *Hrvatska pravna revija*, 2, 11, 2002, pp. 39-53.

³² Jakovac-Lozić, p. 46. Article 119 of the *Die Verfassung des Deutschen Reichs* (The Constitution of the German Empire), in English reads: Marriage, as the foundation of the family and the preservation and expansion of the nation, enjoys the special protection of the Constitution. It is based on the equality of both genders. It is the task of both the State and the communities to strengthen and socially promote the family. Large families may claim social welfare. Motherhood is placed under state protection and welfare.

³³ Jakovac-Lozić, p. 51.

Article 7 guarantees respect for private and family life,³⁴ article 9 right to marry and to found a family³⁵ and article 24 the rights of the child³⁶. Linked to family law issues are also the protection of the rights of the elderly (Article 25)³⁷ and the integration of persons with disabilities (Article 26).³⁸

It is quite obvious that the Charter was not intended to establish new rights. However, as Douglas-Scott argues “... the Charter is innovative in containing, in the same instrument, both economic and social rights along with more traditional civil and political rights“ and in that way it „represents the sharpest relief the *indivisibility* of human rights“.³⁹ The same author correctly emphasises the symbolic significance of the Charter.⁴⁰ Still, has it brought anything new or better in substantive meaning in the family law area? The answer is undoubtedly negative. Let us just *exempli gratia* briefly compare two provisions of the Charter to the two already existing legal instruments, to which all member states of the EU are also parties.⁴¹

As regards the right to marry and to found a family, one could compare Article 9 of the Charter to Article 12 of the European convention for the protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms. Article 12 of the ECHR defines as follows:

³⁴ Everyone has the right to respect for his or her private and family life, home and communications.

³⁵ The right to marry and the right to found a family shall be guaranteed in accordance with the national laws governing the exercise of these rights.

³⁶ 1. Children shall have the right to such protection and care as is necessary for their well-being. They may express their views freely. Such views shall be taken into consideration on matters which concern them in accordance with their age and maturity.

2. In all actions relating to children, whether taken by public authorities or private institutions, the child's best interests must be a primary consideration.

3. Every child shall have the right to maintain on a regular basis a personal relationship and direct contact with both his or her parents, unless that is contrary to his or her interests.

³⁷ The Union recognises and respects the rights of the elderly to lead a life of dignity and independence and to participate in social and cultural life.

³⁸ The Union recognises and respects the right of persons with disabilities to benefit from measures designed to ensure their independence, social and occupational integration and participation in the life of the community.

³⁹ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 651. It should be also mentioned that the Charter guarantees protection of various aspects of family and family life in an indirect manner. Cf. *amplius*: D. Hrabar, 'Prava djece u Europskoj uniji – pravni okvir (Children's rights in the European Union – legal framework)', in: A. Korać Graovac and I. Majstorović (eds.), *Europsko obiteljsko pravo (European family law)*, Narodne novine, Zagreb, 2013, pp. 58, 59.

⁴⁰ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 656.

⁴¹ See also: I. Majstorović, 'Europski pravni kontekst i značenje za hrvatsko materijalno obiteljsko pravo (European legal context and its significance for Croatian substantive family law)', *Godišnjak Akademije pravnih znanosti Hrvatske*, 4, 1, 2013, particularly pp. 86, 87.

Men and women of marriageable age have the right to marry and to found a family, according to the national laws governing the exercise of this right.

Article 9 of the Charter reads:

The right to marry and the right to found a family shall be guaranteed in accordance with the national laws governing the exercise of these rights.

The Charter itself defines that in the „mirroring-rights“, their meaning and scope shall remain the same as in the European Convention, but this does not prevent Union law providing more extensive protection⁴². As McGlynn pointed out soon after the adoption of the Charter „such a provision leaves considerable ambiguity in interpretation and thus enlarges judicial discretion in the interpretation and development of rights, either progressively or regressively, with little control or direction from the Charter“⁴³.

At this point, it is safe to say that the significance of such a legal solution remains unclear even today. It has been stated that the significant change brought by the Charter is separating the right to marry from the right to found a family,⁴⁴ but it seems at the same time that it has already happened in the jurisprudence of the European court for human rights. It omits the so-called heterosexuality-clause, but it should be emphasised that it does not impose on member states the obligation to allow for same-sex marriages.

As regards the rights of the child, the comparison is to be made between Article 24 of the Charter and several relevant provisions of the Convention on the rights of the child, the most important document for the protection of children's rights.

Relevant provisions of the Convention on the rights of the child are:

States Parties undertake to ensure the child such protection and care as is necessary for his or her well-being, taking into account the rights and duties of his or her parents, legal guardians, or other individuals legally responsible for him or her, and, to this end, shall take all appropriate legislative and administrative measures. (Art 3 Para 2)

States Parties shall assure to the child who is capable of forming his or her own views the right to express those views freely in all matters affecting the child, the views of the child being given due weight in accordance with the age and maturity of the child. (Art 12 Para 1)

In all actions concerning children, whether undertaken by public or private social welfare institutions, courts of law, administrative authorities or legislative bodies, the best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration. (Art 3 Para 1)

⁴² Article 53, Para 3 of the Charter.

⁴³ McGlynn, *European Law Review*, p. 584.

⁴⁴ McGlynn, p. 593.

States Parties shall respect the right of the child who is separated from one or both parents to maintain personal relations and direct contact with both parents on a regular basis, except if it is contrary to the child's best interests. (Art 9 Para 3)

Similarly, Article 24 of the Charter of fundamental rights defines:

Children shall have the right to such protection and care as is necessary for their well-being. They may express their views freely. Such views shall be taken into consideration on matters which concern them in accordance with their age and maturity.

In all actions relating to children, whether taken by public authorities or private institutions, the child's best interests must be a primary consideration.

Every child shall have the right to maintain on a regular basis a personal relationship and direct contact with both his or her parents, unless that is contrary to his or her interests.

There are of course some changes and new wordings, but the significance of such a legal provision has, above all, symbolic meaning. There are authors like McGlynn who claim that „the very existence of a specific provision is highly symbolic and represents a significant new phase in the Union's relation with children“⁴⁵ and that „the children's provisions ... are the success story of the family provisions of the Charter“.⁴⁶ It might be said that they were additional motivation for the adoption of further strategies for protection of the rights of the child at the level of the European Union, such as the EU Guidelines for the promotion and protection of the rights of the child,⁴⁷ EU Strategy on the rights of child,⁴⁸ or the most important one, the EU Agenda on the rights of the child.⁴⁹ Nevertheless, the state of protection of children's rights, as well as human rights in general requires coherent changes and concrete developments.⁵⁰

3.2 Charter as an instrument of „bringing Union closer to its citizens“?

As already mentioned, the intention of the Charter was not to establish new rights, but to „bring Union closer to its citizens“, as is one of the goals defined already in the Treaty of Amsterdam in 1997. However, it is clear that this goal is not (yet) achieved. Namely, as

⁴⁵ McGlynn, p. 594.

⁴⁶ McGlynn, p. 597.

⁴⁷ The guidelines are not published in the Official Journal, but are available at: http://eeas.europa.eu/human_rights/guidelines/child/index_en.htm (accessed 1 September 2015).

⁴⁸ Commission communication of 4 July 2006, Towards an EU strategy on the rights of the child, COM (2006) 367 final, 4.7.2006.

⁴⁹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European economic and social committee and the Committee of the regions: An EU Agenda for the rights of the child, COM (2011) 60 final, 15.2.2011.

⁵⁰ See more: Hrabar, *Evropsko obiteljsko pravo (European family law)*, pp. 53-71.

regards the public perception of the Charter, the general awareness is rather high, but the actual knowledge remains low. Namely, while 65 % of the respondents in the latest Eurobarometer survey say that they are familiar with the Charter, only 14 % of them know what Charter really is. Moreover, 35% of the respondents have never heard about it.⁵¹

Furthermore, most of the citizens do not know or understand the significance or the legal scope of the Charter. Unlike many other international legal instruments, such as the European convention on human rights, the Charter of fundamental rights is not „a freestanding bill of rights“;⁵² but it only applies within the field of EU law.⁵³ Majority of respondents say that it applies to all actions of EU member states, including the matters of national competence, which is not true, since it applies to all actions of EU institutions and bodies, as well as the EU member states only when they implement EU law.⁵⁴

Therefore, one can wonder what is the aim of the Charter, apart from bringing numerous human rights provisions in one document? One of the advantages of the system it establishes could be the fact that, as Douglas-Scott states „unlike under the ECHR, where the applicant must exhaust all domestic remedies in order to get a hearing in Strasbourg, applicants may get a ruling from Luxembourg by way of preliminary reference from a domestic court.“⁵⁵ In that way, each national court would indeed be a European court, but at this point, it seems like a long way to achieve it.

On the contrary, such development sometimes seems highly unlikely. Therefore, the questions arise: what significant changes are introduced by the Charter? What was the purpose of such an endeavour? And finally, how does it improve the legal position of European citizens? Providing unanimous answers to these questions is impossible, but one conclusion

⁵¹ European commission: Flash Eurobarometer 416, The Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union, Report, Fieldwork: February 2015, Publication: May 2015, available at: http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/flash/fl_416_en.pdf, pp. 4-6.

⁵² Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 652.

⁵³ Article 51 (Field of application) reads: 1. The provisions of this Charter are addressed to the institutions, bodies, offices and agencies of the Union with due regard for the principle of subsidiarity and to the Member States only when they are implementing Union law. They shall therefore respect the rights, observe the principles and promote the application thereof in accordance with their respective powers and respecting the limits of the powers of the Union as conferred on it in the Treaties. 2. The Charter does not extend the field of application of Union law beyond the powers of the Union or establish any new power or task for the Union, or modify powers and tasks as defined in the Treaties.

⁵⁴ European commission: Flash Eurobarometer 416, The Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union, Report, Fieldwork: February 2015, Publication: May 2015, available at: http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/flash/fl_416_en.pdf, p. 4.

⁵⁵ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 657.

to my mind cannot be successfully challenged. Namely, the legal framework is too complicated. It is more a labyrinth, than a coherent system of protection of human rights of citizens.⁵⁶

As Douglas-Scott puts it „... the most appropriate conclusion to draw on the Lisbon Treaty human rights provisions, and recent Court of Justice case law, might be that it is complexity (emphasis I.M.), rather than human rights protection itself, which has increased most“.⁵⁷ The same concern was raised fifteen years ago by Lowe, who claimed that international law relating to families is becoming „hopelessly complex“ (emphasis I.M.) with a rhetorical question in continuance “surely the very antithesis of the idea of international Conventions?”⁵⁸ The fact is that at this point, there are several protection systems, which stem from different organisations and cause different levels of protection, which is further elaborated in the following chapter.

IV. MULTILEVEL PROTECTION SYSTEMS

Issues of human rights protection in Europe are today resolved within three parallel systems, which De Búrca has long called „three interconnected systems of law: the (as it then was, addition I.M.) European Community, The European Convention on Human Rights, and national law.“⁵⁹

The endeavours for the protection of human rights, and in particular as regards the family law, have long been undertaken within national legal systems, as well as through the activities of the Council of Europe. Its Convention on human rights has rightly been named „European charter of liberty“.⁶⁰ On the other hand, the activities of the European Union (or earlier Community(ies)) were focused on entirely different field, that is the economic suc-

⁵⁶ Similarly, see: V. Bouček, ‘Smjernica kao izvor europskoga međunarodnoga privatnoga prava (Directive as a source of European private international private law)’, *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu*, 58, 6, 2008, p. 1382, or the same author: *Europsko međunarodno privatno pravo u eurointegracijskom procesu i harmonizacija hrvatskog međunarodnog privatnog prava (European private international law in Eurointegrational process and harmonisation of Croatian international private law)*, author’s own edition, Zagreb, 1 *et sq.* On the contrary, there are authors who state that only uninformed claim that EU system looks like a labyrinth, and that it constitutes a coherent, synoptic and unified system of legal norms (*cf.* M. Župan, ‘Međunarodna nadležnost u obiteljskopравnim stvarima – presjek pravne stečevine Europske unije (International jurisdiction in family matters – an overview of EU *acquis*)’, in: J. Garašić, J. (ed.), *Europsko građansko procesno pravo (European civil procedural law)*, Narodne novine, Zagreb, 2013, pp. 170.). However, they still have not presented valid arguments to support such a conclusion.

⁵⁷ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 682.

⁵⁸ N. Lowe, ‘New international conventions affecting the law relating to children - a cause for concern?’, *International Family Law*, 2001, p. 179.

⁵⁹ G. De Búrca, ‘Fundamental human rights and the reach of EC law’, *Oxford journal of legal studies*, vol.13, no. 3, 1993, p. 284.

⁶⁰ *Cf.*: P. Modinos, ‘Effects and repercussions of the European convention on human rights’, *The international and comparative law quarterly*, 11, 2, 1962, available at <http://www.jstor.org/stable/755988>, p. 1108.

cess. As Douglas-Scott reminds us, the EU's „centre of gravity appears to lie elsewhere.“⁶¹ It is of course beyond any doubt for decades now that Community's legislative and executive institutions are bound to comply with recognised fundamental rights and principles, „even though these were not expressly referred to in the Treaties nor in EC legislation.“⁶² The ECJ has also in its early judgements referred to „constitutional traditions“.⁶³

However, in spite all the EU initiatives and efforts, I cannot but agree with the conclusion, that „protection of fundamental rights in the EU has evolved in an *ad hoc*, confusing, incremental way and that there exists no clear, conceptual underpinning to the rights protected under EU law.“⁶⁴ Therefore, at this point there exists „not a lack, but possibly a surfeit of human rights protection within the European legal space“.⁶⁵

According to Article 6 of the Consolidated treaty on European Union, the Union recognises the rights, freedoms and principles set out in the Charter of fundamental rights, but its provision do not extend in any way the competences of the Union as defined in the Treaties.⁶⁶ The core question as a consequence of multilevel protection systems is the one of their feasibility and justification. In general, the issue is whether those parallel systems are equivalent and equally important? At this point, the answer seems to be negative. Moreover, the EU is investing ever more endeavours in order to further its activities in the human rights field, which are of particular relevance for the family law, as shown *infra*.

⁶¹ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 646.

⁶² De Búrca, *Oxford journal of legal studies*, p. 296.

⁶³ Cf. e.g. the wording in the Case C-4/73 *Nold* [1974] ECR 491, para 13: As the Court has already stated, fundamental rights form an integral part of the general principles of law, the observance of which it ensures. In safeguarding these rights, the Court is bound to draw inspiration from constitutional traditions common to the Member States, and it cannot therefore uphold measures which are incompatible with fundamental rights recognized and protected by the constitutions of those States. Similarly, international treaties for the protection of human rights on which the Member States have collaborated or of which they are signatories, can supply guidelines which should be followed within the framework of Community law.

⁶⁴ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 649.

⁶⁵ Douglas-Scott, p. 647.

⁶⁶ It is defined in the same Article, para 2. that „the Union shall accede to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. Such accession shall not affect the Union's competences as defined in the Treaties“. This path has been expected. E.g. De Búrca has long advocated for a formal relationship between the Court of justice and the Court of human rights, arguing that „if principles expressed in the European Convention are taken seriously, it could improve the level of protection given by Member States to the values which each of them has guaranteed under the Convention to respect“. See: De Búrca, *Oxford journal of legal studies*, p. 319. However, at this point, having in mind the Opinion 2/2013 of the Court of justice of the EU on EU accession to the European convention on human rights, this goal is yet to be achieved. The opinion is available at: <http://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?docid=160882&doclang=EN>, (accessed 1st September 2015).

4.1. Union's activities in the family law area

As already mentioned, family law has long resisted the harmonisation and unification activities, as encouraged or envisaged by institutions and bodies of the European Union. However, as Borrás pointed out as early as in 1998, „[t]he issue of family law ... has to be faced as part of the phenomenon of European integration“.⁶⁷

Significant distinction is to be made between substantive and procedural family law. Namely, substantive family law is (still) not under the direct influence of the EU institutions. However, procedural and private international law rules in family matters are growing in number and significance.

The two regulations on private international law issues related to family law in force⁶⁸ are the one on matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility: Council Regulation (EC) No 2201/2003 of 27 November 2003 concerning jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, repealing Regulation (EC) No 1347/2000 (so-called Brussels II *bis* regulation)⁶⁹ and the other regulating maintenance obligations: Council Regulation (EC) No 4/2009 of 18 December 2008 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of decisions and cooperation in matters relating to maintenance obligations.⁷⁰

The third important regulation is in force only for a limited number of member states who have chosen to be bound by it. This is the Council Regulation (EU) No 1259/2010 of 20 December 2010 implementing enhanced cooperation in the area of the law applicable to divorce and legal separation (so-called Rome III regulation).⁷¹ The mechanism of enhanced cooperation, allowing for a multi-speed Europe, was in fact started for the first time in EU history exactly in this matter.⁷²

⁶⁷ A. Borrás, 'Explanatory report to the Convention drawn up on the basis of Article K. 3 of the Treaty on European Union on jurisdiction, recognition and enforcement of judgements in matrimonial matters', Official Journal C 221, 16.7.1998., para 1.

⁶⁸ It should be emphasised how poorly known these regulations are to the wider public, and sometimes even to lawyers. McGlynn justifiably states that it is "tremendously disturbing". C. McGlynn, *Families and the European Union – Law, politics and pluralism*, Cambridge university press, 2006, p. 152.

⁶⁹ Official Journal L 338, 23.12.2003, pp. 1–29. It should be mentioned that this regulation widened the material and personal scope of application, in comparison to the document it has repealed. Namely, the Regulation 1347/2000 excluded parental responsibility towards stepchildren or children adopted by only one spouse in a previous union. Such a development clearly shows the changes in the legal and social understanding of family. Further: Stalford, *International law of law, policy and the family*, pp. 410-434.

⁷⁰ Official Journal L 7, 10.1.2009, pp. 1–79.

⁷¹ Official Journal L 343, 29.12.2010, pp. 10-16.

⁷² Cf. I. Majstorović, 'Obiteljsko pravo kao različitost u jedinstvu: EU i Hrvatska (Family law as diversity in unity: EU and Croatia)', in: A. Korać Graovac and I. Majstorović (eds.) *'Europsko obiteljsko pravo (European family law)'*, Narodne novine, Zagreb, 2013, pp. 19, 20.

As it is confirmed in Article 2 of the Consolidated treaty on European Union, „the Union is founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. These values are common to the Member States in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men prevail.” This provision can definitely be called the “majestic claim.”⁷³ The question which arises is whether these concepts have a common meaning in the EU? Is there a “European consensus” on these matters? I would guess that political, legal and social changes point us to the negative answer.⁷⁴ From the legal point of view, the most intriguing question regarding future development is the question of competence, as elaborated further.

4.2. The issues of competence as an obstacle for further regulation of family matters

One of the crucial issues regarding the EU regulation of private law is the one of competence. Although of utmost importance, this question is often avoided.⁷⁵ Even if the issue seems resolved in other private law areas, this is definitely not the case in the family law field. Namely, there are three basic principles of the EU law which are at the same time three basic obstacles to the widening of the competence of EU in the family law area: principles of conferral, subsidiarity and proportionality, all defined in Article 5 of the Consolidated version of the Treaty on the European Union.⁷⁶

In accordance with the principle of conferral, the Union shall act only within the limits of the competences conferred upon it by the Member States in the Treaties to attain the objectives set out therein. Competences not conferred upon the Union in the Treaties remain with the Member States. In the area of family law, the member states have not (yet) relinquished a part of their sovereignty to the EU.

Principle of subsidiarity means that in areas which do not fall within its exclusive competence, the Union shall act only if and in so far as the objectives of the proposed action cannot be sufficiently achieved by the Member States, either at central level or at regional and local level, but can rather, by reason of the scale or effects of the proposed action, be better achieved at Union level. Although it is often mentioned as a purely theoretical

⁷³ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 647.

⁷⁴ The level of uniformity in certain areas remains to be low, as it was the case also forty years ago. *Cf.* Judgment of the European court of human rights in the Case *Handyside vs. the United Kingdom* (application no. 5493/72) of 7 December 1976, para 48, ... „In particular, it is not possible to find in the domestic law of the various Contracting States a uniform European conception of morals. The view taken by their respective laws of the requirements of morals varies from time to time and from place to place, especially in our era which is characterised by a rapid and far-reaching evolution of opinions on the subject.“

⁷⁵ See: Perišin, p. 1801.

⁷⁶ „The limits of Union competences are governed by the principle of conferral. The use of Union competences is governed by the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality.“

question, the answer to the issue of how is it even possible to fulfil this precondition in the family law field remains open.

Finally, the principle of proportionality requires that the content and form of Union action shall not exceed what is necessary to achieve the objectives of the Treaties. Furthermore, this is a cornerstone of the approach defined already in Amsterdam in 1997, with the Protocol on the application of the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality.

The Lisbon Treaty also states that all the „competences not conferred upon the Union in the Treaties remain with the Member States,“⁷⁷ however the category of the non-conferred competences is not further elaborated.⁷⁸ Therefore, having in mind the aim of this paper, it remains to be defined which are the possible paths EU could follow as regards the family law in the future. Namely, I agree that it would be naive „to think or even hope that there would be no future for the European Union’s family law.“⁷⁹

V. EUROPEAN UNION AT THE CROSSROADS?

It seems at this point that the development of EU interest in the issues of family law has reached a turning point. There are of course several possible scenarios of future activities, but I will focus on three I find to be most realistic: refocusing on economic issues, further and concrete committing to human rights issues and finally, maintaining the *status quo*.

The first option is (re)focusing on economic issues. It might be said that it would be coming back to „the roots“. Having in mind the economic crisis and new challenges put before the EU institutions, such a decision would be self-explanatory. In wider social terms, it would also be needed for the reasons of ageing population, changes in family structures and migration issues.

The second path that EU could follow is making headway in issues of family law, hence promoting its (new) role as the promotor of human rights in Europe. In that manner, the EU would in a certain sense take the regional precedence over the Council of Europe. Such a development would have been unimaginable at the time of their establishment after the Second World War. Since the late sixties of the last century, the Council of Eu-

⁷⁷ Cf. Article 4 of the Consolidated version of the Treaty on European Union.

⁷⁸ The same: Perišin who correctly states that while the Union’s competences are defined as exclusive, shared, complementary, which division does not include the competences withheld to the states. She explains it by the possibilities it leaves open for the European institution to interpret certain competences in a manner which complies to the social and political circumstances and to adjust the Union’s activities to the needs of a certain time, which is usually called „creeping competences“. Perišin, *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu*, pp. 1806, 1807.

⁷⁹ McGlynn, *Families and the EU*, p. 199.

rope has undertaken lots of harmonisation activities, and it has continued to be the most important European organisation devoted to the protection of human rights.⁸⁰

The key question therefore is whether the EU is competent to overtake such a role, being the European human rights patron. At this point, I claim that the answer is negative. The basic principles of subsidiarity, proportionality and conferral of powers still preclude the success of this scenario and represent an obstacle to further development in this direction.

Furthermore, it is not only an issue at the European, but also at the global level. Namely, the actions of EU institutions influence the impact of the conventions adopted within the Hague conference on private international law. As McGlynn states, „Community action actually creates a number of anomalies and disadvantages. The benefits of the Hague convention are that they provide potentially global solutions, rather than ones limited to the member states of the Union...“⁸¹

The other significant question is whether the EU itself has the capacity to fulfil this role. There are authors who claim that the EU not only has the capacity, but „it should in fact become a new kind of post-national human rights institution *lato sensu*.“⁸² It might be concluded that the EU has made efforts to this direction. For instance, the Agency for fundamental rights of the European Union has done remarkable research into human rights and in particular family law issues. Nevertheless, this option would require development of new legal instruments in the field of family law. This scenario asks for introduction of new EU bodies responsible for the protection of human rights. In the area of family law, notwithstanding the relevant scenarios, I would most certainly advocate for the proposal made by Hrabar on the establishment of the European court for the rights of the child.⁸³

The reason can in general be found in the fact that „[t]hroughout its fifty year history, the ECJ has decided many cases which deal with fundamental rights such as non-discrimination, freedom of religion, association and expression. Undoubtedly, in the next fifty years, with both the widening and the deepening of the Union, the Court will be faced with new controversies involving human rights.“⁸⁴ Moreover, it is also true that „... the EU (and CJEU) has no clearly developed, substantive sense of human rights (or indeed of jus-

⁸⁰ I. Majstorović, 'Harmonizacija i unifikacija europskog obiteljskog prava (Harmonisation and unification of European family law)', Pravni fakultet Sveučilišta u Zagrebu, Zavod za građanskopravne znanosti i obiteljskopravnu znanost, Poslijediplomski doktorski studij iz građanskopravnih i obiteljskopravne znanosti, Zagreb, 2009, pp. 35-94, 150-184.

⁸¹ McGlynn, *Families and the EU*, p. 162.

⁸² S. Besson, 'The European Union and human rights: towards a post-national human rights institution?', *Human rights law review*, 6, 2, 2006, p. 326.

⁸³ D. Hrabar, 'The Establishment of a European Court for the Rights of the Child as a New Contribution to the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice', *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta u Zagrebu*, 64, 2, 2014, pp. 181-198.

⁸⁴ Defeis, *Fordham International Law Journal*, p. 1106.

tics),⁸⁵ and furthermore, that „it is likely that the CJEU will continue to determine issues of fundamental rights on a case by case basis, with a particular focus on the proportionality of any infringement of rights, rather than with an eye to the development of a coherent substantive fundamental rights law“.⁸⁶

In the family law area, such a fragmentary system is not adequate and it would definitely pose significant challenges to the protection of human rights. Therefore, a new court would allow for development of a more coherent system, which would enhance the protection of children's rights, as well as human rights in general. It should also be mentioned that children's rights represent one of the family law areas more "prone" to harmonisation, and the situation is similar for instance as regards maintenance issues or guardianship. However, there are also family law issues so linked to national traditions, such as marital law, that the harmonisation, let alone unification, would require not only national consensus, but also a pan-European one. It is unlikely at this point that such an approach would be taken by all EU member states. The example for such a heterogeneous approach is the enhanced co-operation procedure, established by so-called Rome III regulation, as mentioned earlier.⁸⁷

The third, the middle option that I find to be most likely is maintaining the *status quo*. The doubt arising in this case is the relevance of the EU human rights policy and the feasibility of further development of European family law. As Alston and Weiler advocated for more than fifteen years ago, „the Union can only achieve the leadership role to which it aspires through the example it sets to its partners and other States. Leading by example should become the *leitmotif* of a new EU human rights policy“.⁸⁸ One can only wonder whether the recent decision of the CJEU on accession of the European Union to the European convention on human rights is a sign to the other direction.

In all scenarios, here mentioned or not, in regards to the family law issues, an important *caveat* still remains of utmost importance. Namely, as confirmed also by the Preamble of the Treaty on the European Union, its desire is „to deepen the solidarity between their peoples while respecting their history, their culture and their traditions.“ Achieving this goal would demand well-thought actions, as well as balancing the national and "pan-European" interests. Whether the Union has the capacity and interest to fulfil this goal also within the family law area remains yet to be seen.

⁸⁵ Douglas-Scott, *Human rights law review*, p. 678.

⁸⁶ Douglas-Scott, p. 680.

⁸⁷ Cf. *supra* 4.1.

⁸⁸ P. Alston and J. H.H. Weiler, 'An „ever closer union“ in need of a human rights policy: The European Union and human rights', *European journal of international law*, 9, 1998, p. 663.